

Thermodynamics of Some Beryllium Complexes

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The formation of Be-complexes with Py and substituted pyridines have been studied by pH method. Stability constants of the complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method and free energies calculated. The enthalpy changes have been found by the temperature coefficient method and the entropy change calculated by Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. The thermodynamic constants have been interpreted.

Beryllium, though a member of the alkaline earth series, has properties different from other elements of the group because of its small size. Bivalent beryllium takes part in the formation of a number of ligands. Since the study of complexes of pyridine and substituted pyridines with a number of metals has led to interesting results and literature does not reveal any such study with Be^{++} ion, an attempt has been made in the present investigation to work out and interpret the thermodynamic data in the reaction of pyridine and substituted pyridines with Be^{++} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium sulphate was of Johnsons recrystallised variety and the organic bases were either of B.D.H. (pure quality) or German make. The purity of the compounds was checked by the usual methods. A Hungarian pH meter type Op201/1 was used which records upto an accuracy of ± 0.05 . The stability constants were determined by Bjerrum's method. In Tables I, II and III are presented acid dissociation constants of bases, log K values and ΔF , ΔH and ΔS at temperature of 35° and 45°. The ΔS calculated may have an error of ± 7 cal. per degree and ΔH an error of ± 2 Kcal. per mole.

Since the acid dissociation constants were not available at higher temperature they were determined and the values obtained are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Base	pK^a Values	
	35°	45°
Pyridine	5.50	5.00
α -picoline	5.975	5.925
β -picoline	5.66	5.65
γ -picoline	6.28	6.20
2-aminopyridine	6.86	6.75

1. Modern Co-ordination Chemistry by Lewis and Wilkins, p. 54, 55, 56.
2. Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds by Martell and Calvin, p. 149.
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Table II gives the values of the approximate formation constants from the formation constants.

TABLE II

Metal Complexes.	$\bar{n}$	Log K	Temp
Be (py)	1	2.40	35
	1	2.30	45
Be (α -pico)	1	3.531	35
	1	3.42	45
Be (β -pico)	1	2.80	35
	1	2.80	45
Be (γ -pico)	1	3.541	35
	1	3.43	45
Be (2-aminopy)	1	4.37	35
	1	4.24	45

TABLE III

Metal complexes.	$-\Delta F$ Kcals/mole	$-\Delta H$ Kcals/mole	$+\Delta S$ Cals/degree
Be (py)	3.38	4.48	-3.2
Be (α -pico)	4.97	4.98	-0.03
Be (β -pico)	4.08	4.14	-0.18
Be (γ -pico)	4.98	4.98	-0
Be (2-aminopy)	6.15	6.82	4.3

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

The pyridine and the substituted pyridines have low basicity and hence their complexes with beryllium do not have high stabilities. The free energy changes involved are also not high as seen in the Table II and III. There is, however, an increase in the ΔF values and also the stabilities as we go from beryllium pyridinate to beryllium 2-aminopyridinate. This is in accordance with the increase in the basicity of the base.

The plot of Log K of beryllium complexes against pK_a of the corresponding ligands shows an almost linear relationship (Fig. 1). Minor deviations from this relationship may be ascribed to the consideration of enthalpy and entropy as follows.

The heat changes in the complex formation must depend on the nature of hydration of the ions and molecules involved in the reaction. Pyridine is a better electron donor than water, hence it will have a tendency to replace water molecules and get bound to the metal ions with the liberation of energy. As we go to the ligands of higher basicity the tendency to get bound goes on increasing, with consequent increase in the enthalpy changes. Since $\bar{n}$ is same in each case the enthalpy changes is proportional to the basicity of the ligands as found in Table. III.

The minor deviation in the linear relationship between Log K and pK_a must therefore, have been due to the entropy changes. The ligation by pyridine and the substituted pyridine uncharged molecules will not be accompanied by a reduction in the number of ions in solutions nor by the neutralization of charge on the Be^{++} ion. The change in entropy

should not, therefore be considerable. There may be a small positive entropy effect due to the fact that a neutral ligand shields the co-ordinated metal from solvent contacts and makes the solvent less ordered around the complexes than the metal ion.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The ligands are, however, less hydrated i.e., loosely bound with water and undergo a loss in entropy due to their rigid binding with the metal ion in the complexes. The net effect is that in Be-pyridinate we find a negative entropy change which brings down the stability. Substitution of the methyl groups in α , β , and γ position in picolinates is expected

to increase the structure breaking effect of a metal complex on the solvent. This solvent is thus made still less ordered around the complex ion and ΔS becomes less and less negative.

FIG. 3

In the case of 2-aminopyridine the change of entropy is positive. The difference in behaviour may be due to the fact that the 2-aminopy forms a bidentate chelate. Unlike pyridine and α -pyridine, 2-aminopy replaces two molecules of water. In the first case for every water molecule liberated at least one aminomolecule is bound and thus the freedom of rotation lost by one aminomolecule is gained by one water molecule. Since the loss of freedom by the aminomolecule is slightly more than the freedom gained by the water molecule, a slight negative entropy change is observed. In the case of aminopyridinates, however, the freedom gained by two water molecules is not completely compensated by the loss of freedom of the aminopyridine molecule. Thus a positive entropy change is observed. Further the large size of aminopy leads to a greater structure breaking effect of the Be-chelate on the solvent. Thus the greater part of the entropy increase can be attributed to the formation of chelate rings.

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